

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101007990.

Project Acronym:	VITALISE
Project Title:	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure
Project Number:	101007990
Topic:	Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme INFRAIA-02-2020 Integrating Activities for Starting Communities
Type of Action:	RIA - Research and Innovation action
Start date of the Project:	April 2021
Duration of the Project:	36 months

D3.6 Certified Node OS installation image

(Version 3.0, 26/07/2022)

Disclaimer: The information in this document reflects only the author's views and the European Community is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein. The information in this document is provided "as is" without guarantee or warranty of any kind, express or implied, including but not limited to the fitness of the information for a particular purpose. The user thereof uses the information at his/ her sole risk and liability.

Copyright message: ©VITALISE Consortium, 2021. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Deliverable:	D3.6 Certified Node OS installation image	
Work Package:	WP3	
Due Date:	31 July 2022	
Submission Date:	26 July 2022	
Lead Beneficiary:	WITA	
Version:	3.0	
Status:	Final	
Author name(s):	Cristina Molina (VICOM), Gorka Epelde(VICOM), Edwin Dokla (WITA), Mikel Hernández (VICOM)	
Contributor(s):		
Reviewer(s):	Giuseppe Conti (WITA)	Christoniki Maga (CERTH)
Approved by:	Evdokimos Konstantinidis (ENoLL), Project Coordinator	
Keywords:	RAI node, ICT tools, privacy-preserving data processing, remote execution, Living lab digital infrastructure	
Nature:	<input type="checkbox"/> R – Report <input type="checkbox"/> P – Prototype <input type="checkbox"/> D – Demonstrator <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> O - Other	
Dissemination level:	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission) <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

The **VITALISE** Consortium consists of:

Participant #	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Country
1 (Coordinator)	EUROPEAN NETWORK OF LIVING LABS IVZW	ENoLL	Belgium
2	ARISTOTELIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	AUTH	Greece
3	LAUREA-AMMATTIKORKEAKOULU OY	LAUREA	Finland
4	THOMAS MORE KEMPEN VZW	LICALAB	Belgium
5	FUNDACION INTRAS	INTRAS	Spain
6	TREBAG SZELLEMI TULAJDON- ES PROJEKTMENEDZSER KORLATOLT FELELOSSEGU TARSASAG	TREBAG	Hungary
7	ASOCIACION DE INDUSTRIAS DE CONOCIMIENTO Y TECNOLOGIA - GAIA - EUSKALHERRIKO EZAGUTZA ETA TEKNOLOGIA INDUSTRIEN ELKARTEA	GAIA	Spain
8	FUNDACION CENTRO DE TECNOLOGIAS DE INTERACCION VISUAL Y COMUNICACIONES VICOMTECH	VICOM	Spain
9	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	Greece
10	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	AIT	Austria
11	SOCIALIT SOFTWARE E CONSULTING SRL	SIT	Italy
12	UNIVERSIDAD POLITECNICA DE MADRID	UPM	Spain
13	WITA SRL	WITA	Italy
14	ANTHOLOGY VENTURES JSC	AV	Bulgaria
15	VILABS OE	VILABS	Greece
16	FORUM DES LIVING LABS EN SANTE ET AUTONOMIE	LLSA	France
17	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT EINDHOVEN	TUE	Netherlands

D3.6 Certified Node OS installation image

18	ROYAL INSTITUTION FOR THE ADVANCEMENT OF LEARNING MCGILL UNIVERSITY	McGill	Canada
19	UNIVERSITE DE MONTREAL	UDEM	Canada

Revision history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
0.1	06/06/2022	VICOM	Table of Contents
0.2	24/06/2022	VICOM, WITA	Initial contributions
1.0	04/07/2022	VICOM	Version for internal revision
2.0	11/07/2022	VICOM	Version integrating Christoniki Maga's review
2.1	18/07/2022	VICOM	Credentials deleted and changed to under request
2.2	25/07/2022	VICOM	Version integrating WITA's revision
3.0	26/07/2022	ENoLL	Final Project Coordinator Check

Table of Contents

TABLE OF CONTENTS	6
LIST OF FIGURES	6
ABBREVIATIONS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
1 INTRODUCTION	9
1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT	9
1.2 DOCUMENT STRUCTURE	9
2 DEPLOYMENT REQUIREMENTS	10
2.1 MACHINE SPECIFICATIONS	10
2.2 OTHER SPECIFICATIONS	10
2.3 DOCKER IMAGES USED IN THE DEPLOYMENT	11
3 INSTALLATION INSTRUCTIONS	12
3.1 RAINODE.SH INSTALLATION SCRIPT'S INTERPRETATION	12
3.2 POST INSTALLATION	13
4 MONITORING CONFIGURATION	14
4.1 ALERTS	16
5 LL RAI NODE SPECIALISATION	19
5.1 TRANSFORMATION LOGIC-BASED APPROACH	19
5.2 IN-HOUSE DATA TRANSFORMATION TO VITALISE DATA MODEL	21
5.3 MQTT-BASED APPROACH	21
6 REFERENCES	22
7 CONCLUSION	23

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. GRAFANA FIRST LOGIN WINDOW.	14
FIGURE 2. DOCKER AND SYSTEM MONITORING DASHBOARD. THE MOST IMPORTANT INFORMATION ABOUT THE STATE OF THE NODE AND DOCKER IS DISPLAYED HERE.	15
FIGURE 3. GRAFANA LOGS ARE VISUALISED IN THIS DASHBOARD. ADDITIONAL RELATED METRICS ARE ALSO PLOTTED.	16
FIGURE 4. CONFIGURED ALERTING RULES PANEL.	17
FIGURE 5. PANEL FOR THE CONFIGURATION OF THE ALERTING CHANNEL.	18

Abbreviations

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
WP	Work Package
LL	Living Lab
SD	Synthetic Data
AD	Anonymised Data

Executive summary

This deliverable is of software nature, having described its type as OTHER in the grant agreement. The deliverable aims to make a deployable and configurable software package available to Vitalise Living Labs (LL) to enable harmonised data capture and preparation and offer open data processing of controlled data managed by a LL within the VITALISE ecosystem.

Despite being named as “*Certified Node OS installation image*” in the grant agreement, within VITALISE WP3 work team, we have renamed it as **LL RAI node** (and the corresponding deployment image(s)).

This software’s main aim is to provide LLs with common ICT infrastructure tools to upload, capture, and securely offer external researchers access to (controlled) data harmonised with the VITALISE data model. The main services provided by this tool are:

- Dataset upload / capture;
- Transformation to VITALISE data model;
- Anonymised / Synthetic data sharing for local script development by external researchers;
- Remote execution of locally developed scripts with LL-controlled data;
- Registration of the remote experiment results to achieve an immutable identifier.

This deliverable’s implementation has been a result of user requirements capturing (T2.4) and different WP3 tasks targeting the a) general VITALISE service architecture (T3.1), b) VITALISE data model definition (T3.2), c) LL infrastructure API and core communication modules (T3.3), d) Anonymization and synthetic data generation mechanisms (T3.4), and e) RAI node dataset curation, preservation, and remote script execution mechanisms (currently Python is supported) (T3.6).

Communication interfaces of the LL RAI node have been defined and integrated with:

- The Discovery Portal (T3.8): it is the metadata catalogue and external researchers’ portal for requesting/checking anonymous/synthetic data, remote execution of scripts or results registration.
- The RAI Cloud Server (T3.5): it is responsible for registering the experiment results and issuing an immutable identifier to the performed experiment (author, time, script, dataset, and results).

From a technical perspective, tools are being developed using containerisation (Docker) technologies and docker-compose deployment technologies, making them available through a git repository and a Docker image registry, both accessible through the Vitalise GitLab project. As part of T3.6, a deployable package of the LL RAI Node, with all the services installed and configured, has been created to ease the deployment to the Living Lab infrastructures (T3.10).

This deliverable currently presents the result of the second iteration of the LL RAI node (prototype v1) in M16. Future iterations of the developments are planned and will be delivered with tagged branches in VITALISE’s GitLab project. Despite LL RAI node composing modules, further development is foreseen, but no significant changes regarding deployment and monitoring/logging are anticipated. Relevant content of this document will be updated if deemed necessary, but initially, it is not planned.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This deliverable is of software nature, having described its type as OTHER in the grant agreement. The aim is to make a deployable and configurable software package available to Vitalise Living Labs (LL) to enable the harmonised data capture and preparation and provides open data processing of LL-managed controlled data within the VITALISE ecosystem. This document presents the instructions to implement and monitor a LL RAI node instance and the minimum requirements for an installation. Additionally, instructions on the specialisation of the LL RAI node, i.e., how to integrate new sensor types or data sources, are provided.

1.2 Document structure

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- **Section 1** provides information regarding the purpose of the document and its structure.
- **Section 2** includes the minimum requirements for deploying a LL RAI node.
- **Section 3** describes the deployment instructions and the reference to deployment facilitating scripts.
- **Section 4** describes the tools developed to monitor LL RAI node deployment and configure alarms for specific node performance indicators.
- **Section 5** describes the alternatives to extending the LL RAI node by integrating a new data source type, reporting on the steps to be followed per each alternative.
- **Section 6** provides some concluding remarks for this deliverable.

2 Deployment requirements

VITALISE Certified Node software installation is delivered by PaaS (platform as a service) virtualisation containers, using Docker over Linux operating system kernel. For the deployment of the containers, a docker-compose configuration repository is stored in GitLab. Container images corresponding to logic developed for VITALISE-specific needs are kept in GitLab's VITALISE group's container registry. Reused common services container images (e.g., Nginx service) are pulled from Docker Hub. The GitLab Docker-based deployment repository is available at: <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/compolise/-/tree/v1> (v1 represents the current version and will be updated with the version needed).

For the monitoring and logging of the system, a solution based on Grafana, Prometheus, Promtail and Loki have been developed and tested. This solution monitors different containers' performance metrics and jointly presents logs generated by different services.

2.1 Machine specifications

The minimum requirements to run a LL RAI node are enumerated, and extensive performance testing is pending:

- Kernel: Linux 4.15.0 or higher.
- Operating system: Ubuntu 18.04.6 or higher. The installation script is prepared only for Ubuntu, but the setup in other Linux distributions can be feasible.
- Architecture: x86_64.
- RAM: 4GB is the minimum to get the services running. However, more RAM is recommended depending on the number of parallel experiments and expected complexity.
- Swappiness: 60% of RAM.
- Storage: 50GB free for the appropriate functioning of the system. The recommendation is to use at least 250 GB of storage.
 - The storage will be consumed by uploading new datasets and generating new synthetic data and experiment runs.
- Docker-compose version 3.2 (version used in current deployment docker-compose scripts) and Docker engine >17.04.0 (according to the Docker-compose <-> Docker engine [compatibility matrix](#)).

2.2 Other specifications

Once the machine is ready, it is necessary to install the software and register a new RAI Node ID. A bash script pipeline has been developed together with this deliverable to facilitate this process.

The requirements for the execution of the bash script are described in this section:

- Internet connectivity.
- Sudo permissions in the host.
- Full domain name (the convention followed by VITALISE is to use vitalise-node.example.com) for the (virtual) machine hosting the LL RAI node.
- RAI Node ID following UUID4 convention for registering the new RAI Node. It is automatically generated with the installation script if the RAI Node doesn't have one already.
- GitLab token with read-only access to VITALISE's GitLab group:

```
user / password available in MS Teams deliverable folder or  
under request
```

- Open and available ports 80 and 443.

The packages needed for the deployment are automatically installed following the *RAI/Node.sh* script flow. Before installing any package, the script checks if it was already installed in the system. *Git*, *curl*, *Docker-ce* and *docker-compose-plugin* will be installed, among other dependencies.

2.3 Docker images used in the deployment

All the Docker images are automatically pulled with the installation script following the steps described in section 3, but for documentation purposes, they will be listed here. There are two different types of images, the ones with VITALISE's developed code, which are hosted at VITALISE's GitLab Registry, and the external ones that are set with VITALISE's environment variables and configurations.

The developed images are listed below:

- Remote experiment execution logic (Bayaz) image: registry.gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/bayaz:v1;
- RAI Node API (Glokta) image: registry.gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta:v1;
- Synthetic data generation (Synth) image: registry.gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/synth:v1.

Within the external images, three groups are distinguished:

- Infrastructure microservices images:
 - MongoDB image: mongo:4.4.4;
 - File storage service (MinIO) image: quay.io/minio/minio:RELEASE.2021-11-24T23-19-33Z;
 - Message / Task broker (RabbitMQ) image: rabbitmq:3.9.11-management.
- Grafana-based RAI Node Monitoring images:
 - MongoDB metrics exporter image: bitnami/mongodb-exporter:0.11.2;
 - Node metrics exporter image: bitnami/node-exporter:1.3.1-debian-10-r93;
 - Containers metrics exporter image: gcr.io/cadvisor/cadvisor:v0.44.0;
 - Prometheus image: prom/prometheus:v2.33.3;
 - Grafana image: grafana/grafana:8.3.0-ubuntu;
 - Grafana Loki image: grafana/loki:2.4.2;
 - Promtail image: grafana/promtail:2.4.2.
- Reverse proxy and SSL certificate management image: ghcr.io/linuxserver/swag:1.22.0.

3 Installation instructions

The installation process is automatised with the execution of the bash script. This script can be downloaded at <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/rai-installation-script/-/raw/main/RAINode.sh?inline=false> with a web browser or using curl in a terminal, for example:

```
$ curl -o RAINode.sh https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/rai-installation-script/-/raw/main/RAINode.sh?inline=false
```

The script is executed with a terminal in the path of the file:

```
$ sudo -u $USER ./RAINode.sh
```

The installation can take up to 10 minutes, depending on the speed of the internet connection. The most time-consuming part is to pull the Docker images for the deployment.

3.1 RAINode.sh installation script's interpretation

In this section, the process followed in the installation script is explained.

The first part of the script file (lines 1-33) is for welcoming and setting an errors manager. If the installation fails, it will return an error message and the script line where it appeared.

The following lines of the script (34-74) are for external software checking and installation. Initially, it will check available apt packages (*ca-certificates*, *curl*, *GnuPG* and *LSB-release*) and install them in case they are not already installed. Also, if git or Docker or docker-compose are not installed in the host, they will be installed automatically following the instructions described on their official webpages:

- <https://git-scm.com/book/en/v2/Getting-Started-Installing-Git> only *git-all* must be installed.
- <https://github.com/docker/docker-install> is the official installation script from Docker.
- <https://docs.docker.com/compose/install/> only the *docker-compose-plugin* must be installed once Docker has been installed.

The following lines (75-87) are for downloading the VITALISE deployment code. A user and a deployment token have been created; one can use these read-only credentials to connect to the GitLab VITALISE group and download the files:

```
user / password available in MS Teams deliverable folder or under request
```

The next section (lines 88-91) is for the login into the Docker GitLab registry. The credentials for GitLab, the same as the GitLab Docker repository, must be provided:

```
user / password available in MS Teams deliverable folder or under request
```

The last section of the script (lines 92-158) describes the configuration of the environment variables and the deployment of the RAI node. Initially, an RAI node URL is requested. This is the resolvable full domain name of the machine, and the format should be in the form of: *vitalise-node.example.com*. Once the URL is provided, it will be stored in *.env.swag*, *.env.glokta* and *.env.grafana* environment configuration files, and the deployment will start. During the deployment, the necessary Docker networks will be created, and Docker-compose will start the containers. In the first installation of the RAI node, the containers will be downloaded, and depending on the Internet connection, this may be a bit slow. Finally, the RAI node UUID will be generated.

3.2 Post installation

The default variables and the ones configured during the installation are stored in `.env` files inside the `/compolise` folder. They can be modified at any time, but the containers must be recreated to apply the changes. The command used to update the containers is:

```
$ docker compose -f docker-compose-monitoring.prod.yaml -f docker-  
compose-services.prod.yaml up -d
```

It is not recommended to update the `.env.swag` file and the `swag` container, as this container is used to request and maintain the HTTPS credential with Let's Encrypt and the number of weekly configuration update requests per domain is limited. Still, in case it must be updated, run:

```
$ docker compose -f docker-compose-swag.yaml up -d
```

Note: Run the commands in the `/compolise` directory.

4 Monitoring configuration

A Grafana web user interface is deployed as part of the installation process. It can be accessed at `HTTPS://{vitalise-node.example.com}/grafana` (update `{vitalise-node.example.com}` with each deployment's full domain name). Grafana is responsible for displaying each VITALISE node's metrics and logs and the different flows for the services offered by the RAI Node.

In the first login in Grafana (Figure 1), the credentials user: **admin** and password: **admin** should be displayed. It is thoroughly recommended to change the password after the first login. Still, the password can be changed anytime following the link: `HTTPS://{vitalise-node.example.com}/grafana/profile/password`.

Figure 1. Grafana first login window.

After login, six starred dashboards that give relevant information about the RAI node are listed:

- **Docker and system monitoring:** the most important metrics about the state of the node and Docker is displayed in Figure 2, like the node's memory, storage and CPU load.

Figure 2. Docker and system monitoring dashboard. The most important information about the state of the node and Docker is displayed here.

- **Logging Flow:** in this dashboard, the deployment logs are shown (see Figure 3). They are divided into six sections, and overall web communication logging and one per each different flow for the RAI node services:
 - NGINX reverse proxy. This section shows the external communication done with the RAI Node. As means of visualising NGINX reverse-proxy logs a panel is provided;
 - Register Person and Dataset. This section shows the logs and metrics relevant to registering persons and datasets. This flow is required to upload data points later and relate them to a person and a study dataset for future analysis. This section shows three panels, one shows API component (glokta) logs, operations in MongoDB (as a result of adding new person/dataset items) and the available storage in RAI node;
 - Upload Data. This section shows the logs and metrics relevant to uploading new data points (The main related RAI node component is the API component (glokta)). This flow is also relevant to visualising the metadata update that has been successfully sent to the Discovery Portal. This section shows three panels, one shows API component (glokta) logs, operations in MongoDB (as a result of adding new person/dataset items) and the available storage in RAI node;
 - Synthetic Data Generation (can also be used for following Anonymised data flow). This section shows the logs and metrics related to the RAI node components responsible for the API (glokta) and synthetic data generation (synth). This section shows three panels: glokta logs panel, synth logs panel, and the number of objects per bucket (Anonymised data files, SDG models, Hash query files, and Synthetic data files) in Minio, available as result of interaction with this flow;
 - Remote Execution. This section shows the logs and metrics related to the RAI node components responsible for the API (glokta) and the remote execution component (bayaz). This section shows five panels: glokta logs panel, bayaz logs panel, bayaz docker stderr, bayaz celery stderr, bayaz celery stdout, and the number of objects on the experiments bucket in Minio, available as result of interaction with this flow.

D3.6 Certified Node OS installation image

- Register Results: This section shows the logs and metrics related to the RAI node components responsible for the API (glokta). The API logs show logs starting from results registration requests and ending with the registration results reported by the RAI Cloud Server. This section shows one panel with the glokta logs panel;

Figure 3. Grafana logs are visualised in this dashboard. Additional related metrics are also plotted.

- **MinIO Dashboard**: information about the state of the MinIO (Amazon S3 compatible) file storage system. The dashboard comprises panels reporting traffic, node memory and CPU usage, and file management-specific metrics.
- **MongoDB**: information about the state of the database used in VITALISE. This dashboard includes information related to queries, replica queries (not currently used), MongoDB resource metrics (memory, network, disk) and specifically configured alerts.
- **Node Exporter Full**: detailed information about the state of the node. This dashboard contains many subsections with different panel options for the node performance metrics. These panels can be used to define personalised dashboards or to check specific performance metrics not included in configured dashboards.
- **RabbitMQ-Overview**: state of the RabbitMQ message-broker instance and the different queues and messages. The dashboard panels describe resource availability/usage and the number of messages ready to be consumed/delivered/re-delivered. Additionally provides information on total queues, channels and connections.

4.1 Alerts

Grafana has the possibility of configuring some alerts about the important or risky status of the system and deployment.

Figure 4. Configured alerting rules panel.

Currently, four different alert notifications are configured (see Figure 4):

- **Alert CPU load:** if the CPU consumes over 125% of the memory (considering physical and swap memory).
- **Available Memory alert:** if available memory is below 10%, then the alert is displayed.
- **MongoDB's Disk IO Utilization alert:** if MongoDB's average disk i/o utilisation has been above 98% for 5 minutes.
- **Free/Used Disk Space alert:** if the storage usage is over 85% of the total space.

To be informed by Grafana, a notification channel must be configured at <https://vitalise-node.example.com/grafana/alerting/notifications>. Currently google chat option is recommended as email-based notification requires to set up an SMTP server. In the notification settings, using "Default" and "Include image" is recommended, as shown in Figure 5.

The screenshot shows a web interface for configuring alerting channels. At the top, there is a bell icon and the text 'Alerting' with the subtitle 'Alert rules and notifications'. Below this, there are two tabs: 'Alert rules' and 'Notification channels', with the latter being selected. The main content area is titled 'New notification channel' and contains several input fields and checkboxes. The 'Name' field is filled with 'Vitalise alert group'. The 'Type' dropdown menu is set to 'Google Hangouts Chat'. The 'Url' field contains a long URL starting with 'https://chat.googleapis.com/v1/spaces/AAAAZLAZ5m0/messages?key=AlzaSyDdl0hCZtE6v'. Under the 'Notification settings' section, there are four checkboxes: 'Default' (checked), 'Include image' (checked), 'Disable Resolve Message' (unchecked), and 'Send reminders' (unchecked). At the bottom of the form, there are three buttons: 'Save' (highlighted in blue), 'Test', and 'Back'.

Figure 5. Panel for the configuration of the alerting channel.

5 LL RAI node specialisation

With the actual version of the RAI node, LL managers can upload heart rate and step count data deriving from Fitbit devices in the source data format. The LL RAI node is responsible for transforming the input data into the VITALISE data format (https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/tree/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2). Apart from that, a datapoint previously converted to the VITALISE data format can also be uploaded. In this case, it is validated with the VITALISE data model. If the uploaded datapoint is not compliant with any defined data points in the data model, the LL RAI node will notify the user and will not upload it. Additionally, an MQTT-based approach enables LL managers to upload any data stream to the LL RAI node.

This section explains the different processes for adding new input data sources to the LL RAI node. First, how to integrate a new model node in the transformation logic-based approach is defined. Second, the steps to follow to add a new model node to be compatible with the in-house data transformation approach. Finally, adding new model nodes to the MQTT-based method is explained.

5.1 Transformation logic-based approach

To integrate a new model node in the LL RAI node using the transformation logic-based approach, the initial step is to create a new endpoint in the upload router of the API (<https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/routers/upload.py>). The endpoint must be a post request routed as follows: `“/vX/{source}/{model_node}”` (check VITALISE data model for finding model_node names, they’re leaf nodes of the model). Examples: `“/v1/fitbit/steps”`, `“/v1/fitbit/heart_rate”`. The defined function for the endpoint must follow the code presented in Code 1. All occurrences in the function from Code 1 with `modelnode` string should be rewritten with the name of the model node (heart_rate, steps, oxygen_saturation, etc.), and all occurrences with `source` string should be rewritten with the source device (Fitbit, Xiaomi, etc.).

The model structures for the input data format, the transformed data model and the transformation function must be defined. The transformed data format must follow the corresponding data model defined in https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/blob/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2/Data_Model_Schema/vitalise-data-point-0.1.json, and the transformation function must comply with this model. Examples of how this process has been done for heart rate data from a Fitbit device can be found in the actual version of the code. The following list references the corresponding files for this process for the Fitbit Heart Rate example:

- Source datatype data model (Python data structure): https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/data_models/sensors/fitbit/heart_rate_model.py.
- VITALISE data model for heart rate (Python data structure): https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/data_models/vitalise/heart_rate_model.py.
- Transformation function: https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/transformers/fitbit/heart_rate_transformer.py.

Similar files should be created for each new data source and model node that want to be added. It must also be verified that a data model exists for the desired model node in the VITALISE data model (https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/blob/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2/Data_Model_Schema/vitalise-data-point-0.1.json). If it does not exist, the responsible for the repository must be contacted to request the addition of this model node to the VITALISE data model. In addition, the model file should be added to the working repository. We

recommend forking the repository and, after testing the implementation, making a merge request to the official project repository.

```

@router.post("/vX/source/modelnode")
async def source_modelnode(
    source_modelnode_measurements: List[sourceModelnodeItem],
    person_id: UUID = Query(..., description="ID of the person"),
    dataset_id: UUID = Query(..., description="ID of the dataset"),
):
    if len(source_modelnode_measurements) <= 0:
        logger.log_exception("modelnode upload error: Nothing to insert")
        return "Nothing to insert"
    try:
        store = await verify_person_dataset_existence(person_id,
dataset_id)

        if store["person_id"] is True and store["dataset_id"] is True:
            try:
                data = transform_data(person_id, dataset_id,
source_modelnode_measurements, sourceModelnodeTransformer)
                anonymised = await get_dataset_anonymised(str(dataset_id))
                train = False if anonymised else True
                resp = await upload_data(data=data, train=train)
                if resp == 200:
                    logger.log_info("steps data conversion and storage
correctly done")
                    return {"message": "Conversion and storage correctly
done"}
            else:
                logger.log_exception("Metadata update sending to
Discovery Portal failed")
                return {
                    "status": resp.status,
                    "message": "Some error happened while sending
metadata update to Discovery Portal",
                }
        except JSONSchemaValidationError as e:
            logger.log_exception("JSON Schema validation error")
            return {"message": e.message, "number of errors": e.errors}
    else:
        if store["person_id"] is False and store["dataset_id"] is
False:
            logger.log_exception("Invalid person_id and dataset_id")
            return {"message": "Invalid person_id and dataset_id"}
        elif store["person_id"] is False:
            logger.log_exception("Invalid person_id")
            return {"message": "Invalid person_id"}
        elif store["dataset_id"] is False:
            logger.log_exception("Invalid dataset_id")
            return {"message": "Invalid dataset_id"}
    except DatabaseNotEnabled as e:
        logger.log_exception("Database not enabled: " + e)
        raise HTTPException(status_code=500, detail=f"Exception: {e}")

```

Code 1: Function to upload a data endpoint

5.2 In-house data transformation to VITALISE data model

With the in-house data transformation process, the LL manager can upload previously transformed data (using the data model from https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/blob/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2/Data_Model_Schema/vitalise-data-point-0.1.json) to the LL RAI node using the `upload_data` endpoint. The code for this endpoint can be found in <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/routers/upload.py> (lines 57-111).

For a new VITALISE data source type (model node) that is not added to the LL RAI node, the first step is to verify that the data model of the added data source type exists in the VITALISE data model (https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/blob/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2/Data_Model_Schema/vitalise-data-point-0.1.json). If it does not exist, the responsible for the data model repository must be contacted to request the addition of the new data source type to the VITALISE data model. The RAI node data source model definition file should be added to the working repository. On the contrary, if VITALISE data model contains a new model node's definitions but the model is not defined in the RAI node data models path (https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/tree/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/data_models/vitalise), a definition of the new model (Python data structure) must be added, following the heart rate or steps model as a template.

Once it is ensured that the model for the new data type is defined, the class must be added to the list of the input of the `upload_data` endpoint (<https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/routers/upload.py> line 59).

5.3 MQTT-based approach

An MQTT communication-based approach has been proposed recently, and its implementation is still in a draft version.

From the RAI node specialisation perspective, the core idea of the approach is to externalise the transformation logic outside the RAI node. The aim is to communicate the app or sensor-generated data points information through an MQTT communication, encoding the data points' information in VITALISE data model compliant message facilitated by an MQTT-compatible broker. Additionally, a plugin server is provided, enabling plugins to translate existing protocol messages, e.g. FHIR, to VITALISE data points over MQTT communication. Additional planned plugins can store generated communication to disk. This method supports streaming sensor data and batch datasets uploading supported by the previously existing two approaches.

Initial integration of data points to the RAI node is planned by developing a plugin within the Plugin server, monitoring MQTT activity from the plugin and uploading identified data points to the RAI node using the existing RAI node endpoints. An alternative to developing a specific module within the RAI node that will subscribe to the MQTT-broker and ingest them to the RAI node secure storage has been thought of. Development of the solutions will be chosen based on the expected performance and required deployment complexity (The former approach is better targeted for the scenario of supporting MQTT plugin server deployment in a LL private network and deploying RAI node logic in a separate network (including a public cloud virtual machine). In both cases, the aim is to drive the ingestion through the functionalities developed in section 5.2.

As this approach is a work in progress, more information will be provided in future deliverables.

6 References

This deliverable does not contain scientific references; however, different URLs are provided throughout the document, identifying the location of required resources. Next, we collect the resource URLs named in the deliverable:

- RAI node deployment repository: deployment repository is available at: <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/compolise/-/tree/v1>
- Docker-compose <-> Docker engine compatibility matrix: <https://docs.docker.com/compose/compose-file/compose-versioning/>
- RAI node installation script: <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/rai-installation-script/-/raw/main/RAINode.sh?inline=false>
- Git software tracking systems: <https://git-scm.com/book/en/v2/Getting-Started-Installing-Git>
- Docker engine installation script location: <https://github.com/docker/docker-install>
- Docker-compose installation script location: <https://docs.docker.com/compose/install/>
- VITALISE data model repository and branch: https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/tree/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2
- RAI node upload router of the API: <https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/routers/upload.py>
- VITALISE data point model specification file: https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/vitalise-data-model/-/blob/Vitalise_Data_Model_v2/Data_Model_Schema/vitalise-data-point-0.1.json
- Transformation on logic-based approach. Fitbit source datatype's data model (Python data structure): https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/data_models/sensors/fitbit/heart_rate_model.py
- Transformation on logic-based approach. VITALISE data model for heart rate (Python data structure): https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/data_models/vitalise/heart_rate_model.py
- Transformation on logic-based approach. Transformation function: https://gitlab.com/vitalise-project-group/glokta/-/blob/develop/app/vitalise_transformations/transformers/fitbit/heart_rate_transformer.py

7 Conclusion

This document describes the deliverable D3.6 Certified Node OS installation image, which is of software nature, having described its type as OTHER in the grant agreement. Within WP3 work Certified Node OS it has been renamed as *LL RAI node*.

This deliverable reports on the deployable and configurable SW package made available to Vitalise Living Labs (LL) to enable harmonised data capture and preparation and enable open data processing of LL-managed controlled data within the VITALISE ecosystem.

The document starts by introducing the objectives of the deliverable and the purpose of this document in the introduction section. Next, deployment requirements are described in the following section. This section includes deployment machine specifications, complementary network and configuration requirements and a short description of the different docker images used to bundle the solution's deployment. Following a section with installation instructions is provided. At the core of this section, the description of shell script used to automate installation is described, which has docker-compose as a core technology. Additionally, within the installation section, some post-installation configuration instructions are provided. The reader is instructed on configuring the Grafana-based LL RAI node deployment monitoring solution in the monitoring section. Finally, the last section describes the different options developed to specialise the LL RAI node deployment to be able to ingest separate application and sensor-generated data sources.

The current document has described a Docker-based LL RAI node deployment approach implemented for the VITALISE project. This approach has been planned and consistent with future iterations of LL RAI node developments. Current MQTT-based specialisation implementation is in progress, for which more details will be provided in future deliverables.